

INFLUENCE OF COOPERATIVES ON FOOD CROP PRODUCTION IN SHIRORO LGA OF NIGER STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study focused on the Influence of Cooperative on Food Crop Production in Shiroro LGA of Niger State, Nigeria. The data for the study were collected among 115 cooperative farmers through a field survey in 2006. Descriptive statistics were used to analyse the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents while multiple regression analysis was used to estimate the influence of cooperative on food crop Production in the area. The result of the regression analysis revealed that the quantity of fertilizers applied by the farmers, the number of group members (which is a measure of their involvement in cooperative activities) and the other costs of productions affects food crop productivity from the area. The policy implication arising from this study suggest that the government, community based organization and other non-governmental organizations should be encouraged to intensify efforts towards encouraging cooperative organizations through mass campaign and release of more funds and incentives to boost food production from the area

KEYWORDS: Cooperative; Influence; Food; Crop; Production

INTRODUCTION

A Cooperative is a business, voluntarily organized, operated at a cost which is owned, capitalized and controlled by member patron as users, sharing risk and benefits proportional to their participation (Adegeye and Ditto, 1985). Cooperative is an autonomous association of persons united voluntarily to meet their common economic, social and cultural needs and aspirations through a jointly owned and democratically controlled enterprise (International Cooperative Alliance, 2007).

Agricultural Cooperative has the ability to increase food crop productivity among farmers in Shiroro LGA of Niger State. Cooperatives serve as useful instruments for marketing farmers' produce and as avenues for saving and credit facilities as these informal financial institutions are mostly preferred by farmers due to easy accessibility, smallness of scale, and informal nature of transactions (Adeyemo, 1982; Onyenwaku and Ozoh, 1992). Ladele and Ayoola (1997) asserted that food marketing in Kwara State was further strengthened because the state was one of the earliest to embrace food crop marketing cooperative. Adeyemo (1994) reported that members of cooperative societies performed better in terms of gross margins than individuals who were nonmembers.

FAO (2002) reported that in most part of Africa, the culture is basically subsistence where the family cultivates small plots for food needs. Food crop productivity in Shiroro L G A is low due to the fact that farming activities is usually done among poor and low income farmers, cultivating small and fragmented farm land to sustain livelihood. These farmers are often constrained due to their economic status and lack of accessibility to capital and other relevant inputs which would have facilitated the increase in food crop production in the area. Hence, this study is out to study the relevance of cooperatives in increasing food crop productivity in the area.

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Shiroro Local Government Area of Niger State, Nigeria. The data were collected in 2006 though a multistage sampling technique. The first stage was the selection of all the twelve cooperative societies in the area. These are: Kuta Cooperative Society; Sabo-Gida Farmers Cooperative Society; Fadama Users Cooperative Society; Yam Growers Cooperative Society; Groundnut Growers

Cooperative Society; Cassava Growers Cooperative Society; Rainy Season Farmers Cooperative Society; Dry Season Farmers Cooperative Society; Credit and Investment Cooperative Society; Jigiwa Young Farmers Cooperative Society; Bodo Multi-Purposes Cooperative Society and Agricultural Product Marketers Cooperative Society.

The second stage was to randomly select 10 cooperative out of the twelve already selected cooperatives. The third stage was the random administration of 15 structured questionnaires to each of the 10 selected Cooperative Societies out of the twelve. The third stage was the random administration of 15 structured questionnaire to each of the 10 selected Cooperative Societies, making a total of 150 questionnaire. Only 115 were correctly filled and returned and these were used for analysis.

ANALYTICAL TECHNIQUE.

The collected data were analyzed through the aid of descriptive statistics and multiple regression. Three functional forms namely Linear, Semi- Log and Double- Log were tried. The implicit form of the multiple regression is as shown :

$$Y = f (X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5, X_6, X_7, X_8, X_9, e).$$

Where:

Y = output (Kg)

X₁ = labor (Mandays)

X₂ = fertilizer (Kg)

X₃ = farm size (Ha)

X₄ = capital (₦)

X₅ = number of group members

X₆ = age (yrs)

X₇ = cooperative experience (yrs)

X₈ = educational level (no formal education =0, adult education =3, Primary education =6, secondary education =12, tertiary education =16)

X₉ = other costs(₦)

e = error term

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Some socioeconomic characteristics of the farmers were looked into because of their perceived effects on the agricultural activities of the cooperative farmers, these are; gender, age, educational level, occupation and marital status.

Gender perspective of the cooperative farmers as revealed by Table 1.0 shows that majority (60.90%) were male while the remaining 39.10% were female. This is as a result of the fact that agricultural activities were strenuous and required more energy for execution.

The result of the survey on the age of the respondents in table 1.0 also reveals that 74.01% were between the ages of 21 -40 years, 13.04% lies between the age bracket of less than 20 and 41-50 years respectively. This implies that most farmers were in their active productive life whereby they can increase agricultural productivity

Table 1.0 further indicates that 34.70% had no formal education, 21.73% had adult, and primary education. However, 17.30% had secondary education while the remaining 4.34% had tertiary education. This connotes that adoption of innovations may be slow.

The data on the occupation of the respondents as presented on the same table shows that majority (62.20%) were full time farmers while 26.90% and 10.43% were civil servant and traders respectively. The greater

percentage of the respondents being full time farmers imply more time devotion for agricultural for agricultural activities to increase output.

Table 1: Socio – Economic Factors of the Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	70	60.9
Female	45	39.1
Total	115	100.00
Age		
<20	15	13.04
21-30	40	34.78
31-40	45	39.13
41-50	15	13.04
Total	115	100.00
Educational Level		
No formal Education	40	34.78
Adult Education	25	21.73
Primary Education	25	21.73
Secondary Education	20	17.39
Tertiary Education	5	4.34
Total	115	100.00
Occupation		
Farming	72	62.6
Civil Servant	31	26.9
Trading	12	10.43
Others		
Total	115	100.00
Marital Status		
Married	85	73.9
Single	25	21.7
Widow	5	4.34
Widower	-	-
Total	115	100.00

Source; Field Survey, 2006

Table 2.0 : Regression Result of the Influence of Cooperatives on Food Crop Production in Shiroro Local Government Area.

Variables	Coefficient	Std Error	T-Values
b ₀	-156.051	74.435	-2.096
X ₁	0.392	6.566	0.060
X ₂	12.939	6.747	1.918
X ₃	2.212	4.230	0.523
X ₄	2.200	7.595	0.290
X ₅	30.722	17.054	1.801
X ₆	-11.009	11.756	0.936
X ₇	-3.317	5.016	0.661
X ₈	4.311	3.377	1.277
X ₉	-28.193	5.951	4.738

R² : 0 .492, F-ratio : 4.835

Table 1.0 also shows that 73.90% of the farmers were married, 21.70% were single while the remaining 4.34% were widows. This indicates that agricultural production is more practiced by married farmers in order to provide for the needs of their households. This further means increased labour force for agricultural productivity.

Regression Result of the Influence of Cooperatives on Food Crop Production in Shiroro Local Government Area.

The Double log functional form was chosen as the lead equation based on the value of R^2 , T-values and the signs of the coefficients. The explicit result of the multiple regression is shown :

$$Y = -156.05 + 0.392X_1 + 12.939X_2 + 2.212X_3 + 2.200X_4 + 30.722X_5 - 11.009X_6 - 3.317X_7 + 4.311X_8 - 28.193X_9 + \mu$$

The R^2 of the model is 0.492. Which implies that 49.2% of the explanatory variables account for the variation in the crop output. The low R^2 value may be due to the omission of important variables and error made during data collection. The model also have an f-ratio of 4.835 which is significant at 1%. This implies that the explanatory variable, (X_1 - X_9) adequately explain (Y).

Out of the 9 variables included in this model as shown in Table 2.0, only 3 were statistically significant. These are; fertilizer input(X_2) which is statistically significant at 1% and positively related to output (Y). This implies that an increase in the level of fertilizer application on the crop will lead to a corresponding increase in the output of (Y). This is also a clear indication that the respondents have access to fertilizer inputs as a result of their involvement in one form of cooperative or the other.

The number of group members(X_5) is also statistically significant at 10% and positively related to the output (Y). This gives a clear indication that they were able to pool higher resources together in their large numbers than when they were few. The positive sign indicates that an increase in the number of group members will lead to an increase in the level output (Y). Because they can have better collective bargaining power and access to productive resources than on individual bases.

Other cost of production(X_9) is significant at 10% and negatively related to the level of output (Y), this implies, that an increase in other cost of production will lead to a decrease in the level of output. It become glaring that when farmers belong to group (cooperative) they are able to reduce the cost of production. However, labour was not significant but has a positive relationship with the level of output. Also, their years of cooperative experience was not significant in the output of (Y).

CONCLUSION:

Cooperative group is a key phenomenon in the increase of food crop productivity in Shiroro Local Government Area of Niger State, Nigeria. These groups help farmer to come together and discuss ways of solving their problems, increasing food production for nutrition and market value. It will enable the farmers to gain better access to capital and other credit.

Since the importance of cooperative cannot be over emphasized among farmers in Shiroro Local Government Area, it is therefore recommended that the government, community based organizations and other non governmental organizations should be encouraged to intensify efforts towards encouraging cooperative organizations through mass campaign and release of more funds and incentives to boost food production from the area.

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